

Greener Journal of Physical Sciences

ISSN: 2276-7851 ICV 2012: 5.88

Assessing Water Availability in the Odzi Sub-Catchment of Zimbabwe using T.B. Mitchell's Yield Estimation Method

By

**Kosamu Nyoni
Evans Kaseke**

Research Article

Assessing Water Availability in the Odzi Sub-Catchment of Zimbabwe using T.B. Mitchell's Yield Estimation Method

Kosamu Nyoni*, Evans Kaseke

Faculty of Agriculture and Natural Sciences, Great Zimbabwe University, Zimbabwe.

*Corresponding Author's Email: elijahnyoni@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Climate change influences water availability by either increasing or decreasing rainfall and mean annual runoff. This study investigates available water resources of a selected micro catchment of the Odzi sub catchment. It specifically investigates the present commitment levels of available water resources in the sub catchment. Results show that the study area catchment size is about 7% that of Save catchment, yet the net contribution of the yield is about 59% that of Save catchment. This shows that the greatest amount of rainfall most probably falls in this part of the Save catchment. Results also show that the micro catchment has the capacity to supply 433832 people with water for basic human needs as well as for growing food per annum. However, the estimated number of people in the micro catchment is 33409. This means that the amount of committed water is 7.7% of the total available water in the micro catchment. This leaves 92.3% being uncommitted. There is, thus no water scarcity in the micro catchment. In this case, water availability is much higher than demand; the opportunity cost of the water will fall to the next best type of use. Therefore, under such a scenario, inter basin transfers are very possible.

Keywords: climate change, rainfall, runoff, trend analysis, catchment yield, water resources, water availability.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most significant impacts of global climate change will be on the available water resources (Alemaw and Chaoka, 2002). Eriksen and Naes (2003) argue that climate change induced reductions in rainfall amount and raised temperature which led to reduced runoff and increased water stress. This tends to disrupt water dependent activities including those on which livelihoods and food security are based (Nyoni, 2007). Studies on rainfall behaviour in Zimbabwe, Botswana and northern South Africa concluded that between 1971 and 1995 there was a reduction in rainfall totals. Reduction in rainfall has a direct correlation with available water resources. Bernham (1999) and Bernham et al. (2001) also found a recent decrease in mean annual runoff in Southern African catchments that occurred since 1975. They attributed this decline mainly to declining rainfall as well as population increase and changing land use and water use patterns.

Water is described as a finite, vulnerable and an essential resource (ICWE, 1992; Mitchell, 1982). This resource is one of the key natural resources available to human kind whose scarcity can be seen as the most limiting factor to economic growth and social development (ICWE, 1992). Water resource planning requires an estimate of how much can be exploited, where it should be exploited and which sector (agriculture, mines, towns etc.) should benefit (Mitchell, 1982).

2. JUSTIFICATION OF STUDY

Rainfall (and hence available water resources) in Southern Africa is becoming more variable thus failing to meet catchments' water requirements (demands) and this is suspected to be because of climate change in the region (Nyoni, 2007). Studies on rainfall behaviour in Zimbabwe, Botswana and northern South Africa concluded that between 1971 and 95 there was a reduction in rainfall totals and intensities accompanied by increased length and intensity of mid-season dry spells (Foxall, 2004). This results in reduction in available water resources. Alemaw and Chaoka (2002) investigated possible trend in the annual river flow of 502 rivers in the region of Southern Africa and observed that the trends have been linear and declining in general. Bernham, (1999) and Bernham et al. (2001) attributed this decline mainly to declining rainfall as well as population increase and

changing land use and water use patterns. This study is a desk study. It investigated available water resources of a micro catchment in the Odzi sub catchment. It specifically investigated the present commitment levels of available water resources in the sub catchment.

To do this, the study estimated the potential yield of the micro catchment, hence the micro catchment's available water using Mitchell (1967) as well as the commitment levels of the available water in the micro catchment.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Study area

Odzi sub catchment was divided into two sections; the upper section and the lower section (See Figure 1). The sections are shown in figure1 demarcated by a bold line. The upper section of the Odzi sub catchment was selected as the study area and in this study it shall be called micro catchment. It is found in the eastern mountainous areas of Zimbabwe.

Figure 1: Odzi sub catchment with upper and lower sections of sub catchment.

3.2 Hydrology, demography and land use of study area

Population density of whole catchment is about 60 persons per km² in large parts of the catchment; land use is a mixture of communal lands, commercial farms and forests (Lidén et al., 2001). The climate is seasonal with a rainy season from November to March. Odzi sub catchment is part of Save catchment. Save catchment forms part of hydrological zone E which covers the Save - Runde catchment areas. This zone covers 22% of

Zimbabwe's total area. The upper Odzi sub catchment area receives up to 1500 mm rainfall per year while the area west of the Odzi river is much drier and receives about 450 mm/ year and average runoff is 150 to 400 mm yr^{-1} with 174% as the coefficient of variation. The upper mountainous parts (which form part of the study area) receive the highest amounts (Magnus and Magnus, 1999). The irregular seasonal availability of water has led to the establishment of irrigation systems (Lidén et al., 2001). Average potential evapo-transpiration is around 4 mm/day in the catchment area.

3.3 Parameters affecting reservoir yield

According to Kabell (1974), reservoir inflow parameters and reservoir characteristics affect the yield from a given reservoir. Inflow parameters are Mean Annual Runoff (M.A.R), coefficient of variation (Cv) of runoff and monthly recession factor (r). Reservoir characteristics are storage capacity, surface-area curve, evaporation, yield risk factor and pattern of draw-off. For simplicity's sake, draw-offs shall be taken as insignificant. This type of study of estimating catchment potential yield was classified by Zimbabwe's Ministry of Water Resources as Class C. This is the maximum potential catchment yield that can be obtained at the given risk factor over an indefinite span of years. This class therefore represents the ultimate yield that can be derived from a catchment (Mitchell, 1989).

3.4 Data Collection and analysis

Data for five runoff stations (E32, E72, E73, E127 and E129) that pertain to the micro catchment were collected from ZINWA. They were quality controlled before being used to calculate MAR going into dam A from hydrological sub zones E₀₄ and E₀₅ as shown in figure 2.

3.5 Calculating Catchment yield

The term catchment in this study refers to the total water collecting area for any storage work. Reservoir yield is the amount of water that can be drawn from a reservoir in a certain interval of time and it depends on inflow into the reservoir (Sontosh, 1994).

Figure 2: Micro catchment of Odzi sub catchment showing imaginary dam A and hydrological sub zones E₀₄ and E₀₅.

There are several methods used in reservoir yield estimation which are based on empirical formulae and which depend on reservoir catchment characteristics (Moyo, 2005). This study used the T.B. Mitchell's yield estimation method. The MAR used was obtained from analysed long term river flow data for the runoff stations shown in figure 2 according to Mitchell (1982). T.B. Mitchell's yield estimation method analyzed water availability in the micro catchment by using reservoir yield estimations of imaginary dam A shown in Figure 2. This theoretical potential yield is the first approximation to the total amount of surface water that can be developed within a river system (Mitchell, 1982). In this case, the river system was the Odzi river. Dam A was assumed to be collecting runoff water from sub zones E₀₄ and E₀₅. Gauging stations measuring flows going into dam A were as follows; from Zone E 04: E32 and E72 and from zone E05: E73, E127 and E129 (See figure 3 below).

Figure 3: Portion of Odzi sub catchment showing location of runoff stations in the micro catchment.

3.6 Calculating commitment levels of available water in micro catchment

Recommended water requirement for basic human needs is the amount of water that is required by an individual for the purposes of drinking, sanitation, bathing and food preparation. It is estimated at 18.25 m³/ capita/ annum (Gleick, 1996). Water required to grow food for one person is estimated at about 1*10³ m³/ annum (Gleick, 1996). Thus, total water required per person/ annum which was used in this study was 1018.25 m³/ capita/ annum.

3.7 Assumptions

- Full supply area for imaginary dam A is assumed at about 20% of total catchment Area for zones E₀₄ and E₀₅.
- Dam's full capacity assumed to be 2*ΣMAR from Zones 04 and 05.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Potential Catchment Yield Analysis

Potential dam A yield was calculated to be 441749 *10³ m³ using T.B. Mitchell's yield estimation method (See table 1).

Table 1: Catchment yields at 10% risk levels

	Q ₁₀ (10 ³ m ³)
Potential Dam A yield (Total Available water)	441749

The Save catchment yield value was given as 0.75*10⁹ m³ (ZINWA, n.d). Table 2 below shows the ratio of the yield of Dam A to the yield of Save catchment yield given as a percentage. Table 3 below shows the ratio of Dam A catchment area to Save catchment area, given as percentage. Save has a Catchment area of about 7834 Km². Dam A catchment area is about 556.82 km².

Table 2: Yield Comparison between Dam A and Save catchment

	Calculated Value
Yield _{Save catchment}	750000*10 ³ m ³
Yield _{Dam A} /Yield _{Save catchment} *100	58.8 %

Table 3: Catchment Area Comparison between Dam A and Save catchment

	Calculated values
Catchment Area _{Save catchment}	7834 km ²
Dam A Catchment area/Save Catchment area*100	6.4 %

The percentage ratios of yield between Dam A and Save catchment shows that yield in Dam A was about 59% that of Save catchment. In other words, it contributed 59% of the total Save catchment yield. However, in terms of area, Dam A Catchment was found to be about 6.4% that of Save Catchment. This is quite a significant contribution to yield judged from the small area with the 59% contribution to Save Catchment’s total yield. According to Magnus and Magnus (1999), the upper catchment area receives the highest amount rainfall per year of up to 1500 mm. Imaginary dam A is located in this upper catchment area of Odzi sub catchment. The Odzi sub catchment forms part of upper Save Catchment (See figure 1).

4.2 Calculations based on available water in micro catchment

Table 4: Calculated committed, uncommitted available water and number of persons satisfied by available water for micro catchment

	Calculated Value
(1) Total yield of micro catchment (Q) (Total available water)	441749 * 10 ³ m ³
(2) Per capita water requirement (Adopted from (Gleick, 1996))	1018.25 m ³ /capita/annum
(3) Number of persons that can satisfactorily be supplied by available water/annum (= (1)/(2))	433832
(4) Population density of Odzi sub catchment	60 persons/ km ²
(5) Total area of micro catchment	556.82 km ²
(6) Average micro catchment population (= (4)*(5))	33409
(7) Committed available water/ annum in micro catchment (= (2)*(6))	34018.71*10 ³ m ³
Committed available water/ annum in micro catchment as a percentage of total available water	7.7%
(8) Uncommitted available water/ annum in micro catchment (= (1)-(7))	407730.29 *10 ³ m ³
Uncommitted available water/ annum in micro catchment as a percentage of total available water	92.3%

Results above showed that the micro catchment had the capacity to supply 433832 people with water for basic human needs as well as for growing food per annum. However, the estimated number of people in the micro catchment was found to be 33409. This means that the amount of committed water was 7.7% of the total available water in the micro catchment. This leaves 92.3% being uncommitted. There was, therefore, no water shortage in the micro catchment.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Results have shown that the micro catchment was currently far from being labeled water short. In this case, water availability is much higher than demand; the opportunity cost of the water will fall to the next best type of use. Inter basin transfers could be a good move especially in Zimbabwe where other catchment areas like the Mzingwani catchment are already water stressed. This would certainly come as a relief to those dwelling in the water stressed catchment. Results have further shown that the micro catchment had a total yield value of about $0.44 * 10^9 \text{m}^3$. This was about 59% of the total yield of the Save catchment based on calculations. Study area catchment size was about 6.4% that of Save, yet the net contribution of the yield from the study area is about 59%. This showed therefore, that the greatest amount of rainfall most probably fell in that part of the Save catchment.

The study strongly recommended that though there was excess water in the micro catchment, measures were still supposed to be put in place to conserve every drop of water as this would be a wise move agreeable with an old adage which says that a stitch in time saves nine. Climate change is there to stay and population is on the increase, thus with time the excess water resource will eventually become fully committed.

REFERENCES

- Alemaw BF, Chaoka TR (2002). Trends in the flow regime of the Southern African rivers as visualized from Rescaled Adjusted Partial Sums (RAPS). *African Journal of Science and Technology (AJST), Science and Engineering Series*, 3 (1):69-78.
- Bernham FA (1999). Development and Application of a GIS –based regional hydrological variability and environmental assessment system (RHVEAS) for Southern Africa region. Ph.D. Dissertation, University of Dar Es Salaam, Tanzania.
- Bernham FA, Zaake BT, Kachroo RK (2001). A study of variability of annual river flow of the Southern African Region. *Hydrol.Sci.J.*46 (4):513-524.
- Eriksen S, Naes LO (2003). Pro-poor Climate Adaptation: Norwegian Development Corporation and Climate Change Adaptation. An Assessment of Issues, Strategies and Potential Entry Points. November, 2003 report commissioned by NORAD. Oslo: CICERO.
- Foxall D (2004). Daily Rainfall variability in Southern Central Africa. An Analysis of Present and Future Behaviour. PhD studentship, 2000-2004. Norwich: Climate Research Research Unit, University of East Anglia.
- Gleick PH (1996). Basic Water Requirements for Human Activities: Meeting Basic Needs. *Water International*, 21:83-92.
- Hulme M, Sheard N (1999). Climate Change Scenarios for Zimbabwe. Climate Research Unit, UK.
- ICWE (1992). The Dublin Statement and Report of the Conference. International conference on water and the environment: development issues for the 21st century: 26-31 January 1992, Dublin
- Kabell TC (1974). The philosophy of reservoir yield and operational system for the maximum utilization of water resources. Harare, Zimbabwe.
- Lidén R, Harlin J, Karlsson M, Rahmberg M (2001). Hydrological modeling of fine sediments in the Odzi River, Zimbabwe. *Water SA*, 27(3).
- Magnus C, Magnus R (1999). Assessment of Suspended Sediment Variability in the Odzi River, Zimbabwe. Working Group for Tropical Ecology at Uppsala University.
- Mitchell TB (1967). A guide to reservoir yield. MWRD Paper.
- Mitchell TB (1982). Potential water yield in semiarid regions. Optimal Allocation of Water Resources. Proceedings of the Exeter Symposium, July 1982, IAHS Publ. No. 135.
- Mitchell TB (1989). Notes on Programme Yield 98. Internal circular, Ministry of Rural Resources and Water development, Zimbabwe.
- Moyo B (2005). Impact and adaptation of climate variability on water supply reservoirs yields for the City of Bulawayo-Mzingwane Catchment. MSc. Dissertation, University of Zimbabwe, Mount Pleasant, Harare.
- Nyoni K (2007). An Assessment of Climate Change and Possible Impact on Available Water Resources on the Odzi sub-catchment in Zimbabwe. Dissertation, Department of Civil Engineering, University of Zimbabwe, Mount Pleasant, Harare.
- Sontosh D. (1994). *Water Supply Engineering*. New Delhi, India.
- ZINWA (n.d). Old blue book, Government of Zimbabwe.